

possess antiviral activity³. 4-Aryl-3-(4-chlorophenylthiomethyl)-5-mercaptoacetyl-*N*-arylidene-1,2,4-triazoles have shown antiviral activity against tobacco mosaic virus³. These findings prompted us to undertake synthesis of the title compounds (Scheme 1) and evaluate their antiviral activity. The compounds were characterised by their ir and pmr spectra and elemental analysis.

Scheme 1

Synthesis and Antiviral Activity of 4-Aryl-5-(3,5-dinitrobenzoyl)-3-mercapto-*N*-arylidene-acetylhydrazinotriazoles

ARCHANA JYOTI SRIVASTAVA, SANJAY SWARUP
and

V. K. SAXENA*

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University,
Lucknow-226 007

and

B. L. CHOWDHURY

Department of Virology, Central Drug Research Institute,
Lucknow-226 007

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VARIOUS antiviral activities¹ have been found to be associated with the triazole derivatives. Some cyclated 1,2,4-triazole derivatives are known to

All the compounds (7a-i; Table 1) were tested for their *in vitro* antiviral activity against Ranikhet disease virus (RDV) on chorioallantoic membrane of

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 7a-i*

Compd. no.	Ar	R	M p. °C	Mol. formula
7a	C ₆ H ₅	H	126	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₈
b	-CH=CHC ₆ H ₅	H	90	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₈
c	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	H	102	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₇ O ₈
d	C ₆ H ₅	Cl	160	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₈ Cl
e	-CH=CHC ₆ H ₅	Cl	98	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₇ O ₈ Cl
f	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	Cl	165	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₇ O ₈ Cl
g	C ₆ H ₅	OCH ₃	138	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₇
h	-CH=CHC ₆ H ₅	OCH ₃	128	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₇ O ₇
i	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	OCH ₃	98	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₇ O ₇

*All compounds showed satisfactory C, H and N analyses; yields 60-75%.

chick embryo. The strain of the RDV was the same as employed by Babbar and Dhar⁴. Chorioallantoic membrane of 10-days old chick embryo was taken and the culture was prepared according to the reported method⁶. Results of the activity revealed that nearly 50% of the compounds were effective against the virus. Maximum activity (50%) was given by compound 7e. Compounds 7d, 7f and 7i also possessed some activity. The results indicate that the presence of *p*-chloro- and *p*-methoxyphenyl groups at N-4 of the triazole nucleus enhances the activity of the compounds. In general these compounds showed only moderate activity against RDV.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected and the purity was checked by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Varian A 60D instrument.

3,5-Dinitrobenzoic acid hydrazide⁶ (1) and substituted-phenyl isothiocyanates⁷ (2) were reacted to yield the 4-aryl-5-(3,5-dinitrobenzoyl)thiosemicarbazides (3). The latter were cyclised by alkali to the 4-aryl-5-(3,5-dinitrobenzoyl)-3-mercapto-1,3,4-triazoles (4) following reported method^{8,9}.

4-Aryl-5-(3,5-dinitrobenzoyl)-3-mercaptoethylaceto-1,3,4-triazoles (5a-c): A mixture of 4 (0.01 mol) and chloroethyl acetate (0.01 mol) in acetone containing a little amount of K₂CO₃ was refluxed for 6 h. Excess solvent was then removed and the resulting viscous mass was treated several times with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°). Solid thus obtained was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol: 5a (R=H), m.p. 120° (Found: C, 49.8; H, 3.3; N, 15.2. C₁₉H₁₈N₆O₇S requires: C, 49.9; H, 3.3; N, 15.3%); 5b (R=Cl), m.p. 104° (Found: C, 46.0; H, 3.3; N, 15.3. C₁₉H₁₄N₆O₇SCl requires: C, 46.4; H, 2.9; N, 14.2%); 5c (R=OCH₃), m.p. 100° (Found: C, 49.2; H, 3.4; N, 14.3. C₂₀H₁₇N₆O₈S requires: C, 49.3; H, 3.5; N, 14.4%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 730–1 715 (C=O), 1 610–1 600 (C=N), 1 550–1 530 and 1 320–1 310 cm⁻¹ (NO₂).

4-Aryl-5-(3,5-dinitrobenzoyl)-3-mercaptoacetylhydrazino-1,3,4-triazoles (6a-c): A mixture of 5a-c (0.01 mol), hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) and ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 6 h and the excess solvent removed. The resulting solid was washed with cold water and recrystallised from ethanol: 6a (R=H), m.p. 89° (Found: C, 45.9; H, 2.9; N, 22.1. C₁₇H₁₃N₇O₆S requires: C, 46.9; H, 2.9; N, 22.1%); ν_{\max} 3 325–3 320 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 7.06–7.80 (8H, m, Ar-CH), 11.60–11.72 (1H, s, NH), 3.50–3.80 (2H, s, S-CH₂-N) and 1.20–1.65 (2H, d, NH₂); 6b (R=Cl), m.p. 98° (Found: C, 42.5; H, 2.5; N, 20.4. C₁₇H₁₂N₇O₆Cl requires: C, 42.7; H, 2.5; N, 20.5%); 6c (R=OCH₃), m.p. 95° (Found: C, 45.5; H, 3.1; N, 20.6. C₁₈H₁₅N₇O₇S requires: C, 45.7; H, 3.2; N, 20.7%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 730–1 715 (C=O), 1 610–1 600 (C=N), 1 550–

1 530 and 1 320–1 310 (NO₂) and 3 325–3 320 cm⁻¹ (NH).

4-Aryl-5-(3,5-dinitrobenzoyl)-3-mercapto-N-arylideneacetylhydrazino-1,3,4-triazoles (7a-i): An equimolar mixture of 6a-c and an aromatic aldehyde in pyridine (25 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then poured on crushed ice and concentrated HCl was added dropwise. Solid thus obtained was washed with water and recrystallised from chloroform: 7a ν_{\max} 1 730–1 720 (C=O), 1 640–1 620 (C=N), 1 550–1 530 and 1 320–1 310 (NO₂) and 3 325–3 320 cm⁻¹ (NH); 7d δ 7.06–7.80 (8H, m, Ar-CH), 11.68 (1H, s, NH), 6.40–6.50 (3H, t, -CH=N) and 3.50–3.76 (2H, s, S-CH₂-C).

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